

Review

Methods to Increase the Grinding Efficiency of Spices – A Review

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Accepted: 26 April, 2020; Online: 2 May, 2020

DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3780393>

Abstract: This paper aims to review the current improvements in the grinding process of spices. Grinding is an important step in postharvest processing of spices. Therefore, it requires special attention in preserving aroma and flavor compounds present in them. Overall temperature increases significantly during grinding which results in loss of a considerable fraction of aroma and flavor components in spices. During grinding, quality of spices is often limited by thermal damage to the ground component. The amount of heat entering the workpiece must be controlled in order to avoid thermal damage. This is one of the main limitations of the grinding process which is to be important to understand how to overcome the factors which affect the grinding temperature. There are several methods that are efficient for different types of spices available in the world. Therefore, it is important to use correct technologies and measures to secure the quality of the spice product.

Keywords: Aroma & Flavor, Grinding Efficiency, Spices, Thermal damage

Introduction

Sri Lanka is a land of spices with all the food within the teardrop island laden with rich flavors. Spices provide aroma, color, pungent flavor, taste and sometimes even texture to food (Barnwal *et al.* 2014). These characteristics are an integral part of food and agricultural commodities. Spices contain a good amount of minerals like potassium, manganese, iron and magnesium (Lobo *et al.* 2010).

Epidemiological studies indicate that cancer incidence in countries like India where spices are consumed daily is highly lower (94/100,000) than those where spices aren't consumed like United States (318/100,000) suggesting the potential role of spices in cancer prevention (Kunnumakkara *et al.* 2018). Processing and trade of spices have always been an important industry. The value and volume of spices being produced and its market expected to continue to increase by about 7.1% CAGR (Compound Annual Growth Rate) in the world (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Spices and herbs extract market estimates and forecast (source: Mordor Intelligence)

Spices can come from almost any part of a plant like seeds, fruits, leaves, roots, barks, floral buds or other plant substances. Customers have an increasing preference for ready-to-use spices that save time while cooking without compromising the flavor. In view of this the demand for spices in powdered form (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. U.S organic spices market size, by product, 2015-2025 (USD Billion) (source: www.grandviewresearch.com)

As shown by Fig. 2, usually the powder form of spices is used as an additive ingredient to food products due to its characteristic taste and flavor to varied food preparations. For example, curry powder is made from blend of several spices, the amount varying from minimum five to quite twenty spices, depending on the end use. The explanation for reducing size of a material are to make appropriate particle size for subsequent processing or end use, create a free-flowing material, improve material blending, and stop segregation by making products in several size ranges. Powdering increases the material's surface area to enhance the material's reactivity and drying efficiency (Wennerstrum *et al.* 2002). Therefore, there is a requirement for converting the original form to powder form of spices before its use.

Grinding is one among the foremost common unit operations used to prepare ground agricultural materials including spice powders for consumption. Spice is converted to powder by the mechanical process of grinding which results in increase the temperature as high as 43-95°C under ambient or normal conditions which results in loss of essential oils and quality deterioration of the obtained powder (Singh & Goswami 2007).

Grinding is an abrasive machining process that uses a cutting tool in order to make powder form of spices. It is one of the most power consuming operations because only 1 % of the energy is utilized for loosening the bond between particles, whereas almost 99% of input energy is dissipated as heat, causing rise in the temperature of the ground product (Meghwal & Goswami 2010). Power consumption in grinding, size of particles and increase in the surface area depends on the initial size, shape and strength of the particles or material, the kind of grinder used for the operation and the fixing of operating parameters for running the grinder such as temperature, size of sieve, number of rotor ribs etc (Das 2001).

The main aim of spice grinding is to get smaller particle size with good product quality in terms of flavor and color. The aroma and flavor of spices are of importance. Grinding process should not harm the physical properties and quality of spices. Within the normal grinding process, heat is generated when energy is used to fracture particles into smaller sizes (Schweiggert *et al.* 2007). Normally, grinding leads to temperature increase, thereby decreasing the quality of product.

Temperature increase causes thermal damage in ground material. Therefore, this should be minimized so as to prevent loss of volatile oil or flavoring components in spices.

Thermal damage is detrimental to the machine part imparting grinding effect and may reduce its fatigue life and wear resistance dramatically. As a result, the component may fail long before its expected life. To satisfy expected standards of quality a machine part must retain good wear resistance while preserving its expected life. Remedies to thermal damage which compromises wear resistance and part life must be sought. Calculation of temperature and its effect on thermal damage to the material undergoing grinding has been carried out by Malkin & Guo (2007), suggested that a better product could be obtained by reducing the temperature of the two rubbing surfaces.

Due to the heat generated during production leads to powder of poor quality that doesn't conform to the international quality standards. As a result, either fetches lower prices or not accepted by the importing countries. There are several possible ways for the heat generated in grinding to dissipate. It can be either changing grinding mechanisms or by alternating the grinding machine.

Grinding mechanisms that can be used,

1. Cooling system assisted grinding mechanism
 - 1.1 Refrigeration method
 - 1.2 Mist jet cooling method
 - 1.3 Ultrasonic assisted grinding mechanism
2. Ambient cryogenic grinding mechanism

Methods by alternating the grinding machine parts,

1. Use a sharp wheel, soft wheel grades, frequent dressing.
2. Use high work speed and optimum wheel speed.
3. Introduce an optimum number of slots into the grinding wheel.
4. Use coarse dressing rather than fine dressing.
5. When possible, use grinding fluid.
6. Use a Cubic Boron Nitride (CBN) wheel.

Further, each method describes how it prevents the temperature increase during grinding.

Grinding mechanisms

1. Cooling system assisted grinding mechanism

1.1.Refrigeration method

Temperature increase during grinding is often addressed by maintaining the continuous low temperature within the grinder thereby, retaining most of the flavor strength per unit mass of spice. It often minimizes to some extent by circulating cold air or water around the grinder. But this system technique is not sufficient enough to significantly reduce the temperature rise of the product (Meghwal & Goswami 2010). Precooling of the raw spice and the continuous low temperature maintained within the grinder reduces loss of volatile oil, thereby, retaining most of the flavor strength per unit mass of spice (Mathew & Sreenarayanan 2007).

Development of low temperature grinding mill designed by cooling coil (evaporator), capillary tube, condenser, refrigerant and compressor is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Cooling system assisted grinding mechanism (Refrigeration method)

(Source: Shelake 2019)

It is very efficient in reducing the rate of increase in temperature inside the grinder. This helps in retaining the essential components of the food products in terms of nutrition, flavor and aroma.

1.2.Mist jet cooling method

Traditional cooling methods supported large amounts of water-oil emulsions can be both ineffective and environmentally unacceptable. A replacement approach to this present problem has been devised utilizing the high penetrating power of fast air jets combined with a water/ soap

mist to greatly improve convective cooling and lubrication along the arc of cut (Babic *et al.* 2005).

One of the popular types of grinder was subjected to adding water spray system during milling during which water is taken into account to be the one with the highest latent heat among the other substances and also which could be used for absorbing energy dissipated during size reduction thereby preserving the quality of product. Babic *et al.* (2005), mentioned that the jet cooling method further improved by introducing a small amount of water droplets into the air jets to increase their heat transfer potential and their ability to clean the wheel. As water is not a good grinding lubricant, the addition of some substance with good lubricity like liquid soap, which doesn't degrade the environment, lubricate the cutting zone to such an extent that significant reductions in tangential forces and grinding temperatures have been achieved.

1.3. Ultrasonic assisted grinding mechanism

In conventional grinding of hard to chop spices, surface burning, high tool wear, thermal stress, re deposition and adhesion of chips to the grinding wheel and workpiece occur visibly unless it is carried out at low speeds and with high volume of cutting fluid.

Ultrasonic assisted grinding is an efficient machining process which improves the machinability of hard to chop spices by changing the kinematics of the process. The way of grinding using ultrasonic vibration is shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 4. Ultrasonic assisted grinding mechanism

(Source: Lauwers *et al.* 2010)

According to Mohsen *et al.* (2012), improvements in forces and surface quality could also be attributed to the variation within the dynamics of the grinding process when vibrations are applied. Ultrasonic vibration generates impact loads, lower contact surface, variation in cutting depth, self-sharpening and improvement in lubricant penetration that results in change in grinding forces and surface quality.

Finally concluded that, grinding forces have been reduced at all ultrasonic assisted grinding experiments. And also, surface roughness shows a mean average of 10% improvement when ultrasonic vibration is imposed. Due to the reduction of grinding forces and improvement of surface roughness in ultrasonic assisted grinding, grinding at higher cutting depth and cutting speed with lower coolant consumption are possible which cause higher production rate and lower manufacturing cost. Furthermore, the decrease in coolant consumption is desirable for environmentally conscious manufacturing.

2. Ambient cryogenic grinding mechanism

Cryogenic grinding also referred to as freezer milling is the act of cooling or chilling a material and then reducing it into a small particle size. It's the technique of pulverizing spices at sub-zero temperatures (-17.78°C), to attenuate the loss of essential oils. During this mechanism, when grinder is chilled by dry ice, liquid CO_2 or nitrogen, spices can be often finely ground to powders (Saxena & Soni 2013). Cryogenic grinding mechanism using liquid nitrogen as cooling agent is shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Cryogenic grinding mechanism using liquid nitrogen as coolant

(Source: Singh & Goswami 1999)

In fact, during conventional grinding, temperature rises to over 90⁰ C can occur (up to 95⁰ C have been reported) due to the friction induced heat during particles fracture into smaller sizes. This local temperature increase causes important losses of aroma, nutrients and flavor components as well as considerable quality degradation (Schweiggert *et al.* 2007).

Many authors have underlined that the energy input to the grinder is converted into heat whereas only 1% is used for actual size reduction (Meghwal & Goswami 2014). But in cryogenic grinding, Balasubramanian *et al.* (2012) have reported a rise in volatile oils and flavor strength (up to two-fold) in ground spices. Finally, in modern spices milling, cryogenic grinding has shown a promising pathway for enhancing the quality standard of ground spices on the basis of the appearance (color), aroma and flavor characteristics of the volatile oil with high consumer acceptance (Murthy & Bhattacharya 2008).

Sharma *et al.* (2014), reported the spray of liquid CO₂ directly into the grinding mill and found that nearly all experiments without spraying liquid CO₂ caused choking of sieve and ultimately breakdown of the mill. Further this was confirmed by Singh & Goswami (1999), the loss of volatile matter is often significantly reduced by using liquid N₂ or liquid CO₂ that gives the refrigeration needed to precool the spices and maintain the designed low temperature by absorbing the heat generated during grinding operation.

Balasubramanian *et al.* (2012), explained that efficiency of a cryogenic grinder hinges on its design and raw material properties (physical and thermal) to be ground and cryogenic grinder design which includes proper selection of material, pre-cooler, liquid N₂ distribution device, a grinder, temperature controls, and sensors. He reported that modified plank equation is used to calculate the resident time of spice seeds in liquid and gaseous state N₂. He acknowledged that cryogenic pre-coolers should be designed to scale back the temperature below the brittle point of spice seeds and its oil, before it enters the grinder.

Alternatives in grinding machine

1. Use a sharp wheel, soft wheel grades, frequent dressing

The quality, characteristics and rate of grinding wheel wear can be affected by contributions of the characteristics of the material of the workpiece, the temperature increase of the workpiece and the rate of wear of the grinding wheel itself. Moderate wear rate allows for more consistent material size. Maintaining stable grinding forces is preferred instead of high wheel wear rate which can decrease the effectiveness of material removal from the workpiece (Rome & Brian 2009).

The lifespan of the grinding wheel and final surface properties of the workpiece are directly affected by the operating cutting temperature. Heat generated during grinding penetrates the grinding wheel and the workpiece which can cause dimensional errors due to thermal expansion (Kaczmarek 2008).

The addition of grinding fluids can effectively control cutting temperatures to scale back heat induced surface effects on the wheel and workpiece (Marinov &Valery 2012). This can be accomplished either by reducing the heat generated in or by improving heat removal from the grinding zone.

2. Use high work speed and optimum wheel speed

The heat generated also depends upon the time of contact between the wheel and the workpiece. Hence by increasing the work speed, the contact time could also be reduced which successfully leads to less heat evolution and less heat entering the workpiece. In early 1986, King and Hahn have discussed the influence of wheel speed on grinding power and have determined experimentally that very low or very high wheel speed may require high grinding power.

This result show that optimum wheel speed in most cases is within the range of 8000-10000 fpm; at higher or lower speeds, thermal damage is more likely to occur.

3. Introduce an optimum number of slots into the grinding wheel

The introduction of slots within the grinding wheel has beneficial effects on the critical heat flux for burning. It should be noted that the higher the critical heat flux, the lower the probabilities are that film boiling or burnout develops.

4. Use coarse dressing rather than fine dressing

When compared fine dressing and coarse dressing, coarse dressing results in higher values of critical heat flux (Darafon *et al.* 2016). Therefore, we will conclude that it results in lower possibility of developing thermal damages.

5. When possible, use of grinding fluid

Proper choice of fluid type and application method plays a crucial role in avoiding thermal damage. The selection whether to use a neat oil or a water based fluid is significant. It is widely accepted that oil provides good lubrication but poor cooling.

The use of grinding fluids is effective in preventing thermal damage since fluids not only remove heat from the grinding zone but also lubricate to scale back the friction between the wheel and the workpiece.

Use of oil reduces the friction within the grinding zone and can end in lower grinding power. Despite its poor cooling properties, the film boiling phenomenon is fairly uncommon for oil because the film boiling temperature for oil ($\approx 300^{\circ}\text{C}$) is high. Water based fluids have good cooling properties, but they provide lower lubrication and have a much lower film boiling temperature.

6. Use a Cubic Boron Nitride (CBN) wheel

The CBN itself removes an outsized fraction of the heat from the grinding zone (Herman & Markul 2004). Lower maximum temperature produced by CBN wheels as compared to conventional alumina wheels, is said to be due to the good thermal conductivity of CBN.

Conclusion

Although the spices are consumed throughout the world, few technology improvements on spice processing are available. It's concluded from this study that the novel technologies discussed here, provide solutions for improving aroma, flavor, preservation of higher volatile oil content and clogging of sieve which are found to be serious in normal conventional grinding.

Therefore, it's important that these technologies must be introduced to ensure the quality of the spice products.

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